

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Change detection of the Köppen climate zones in Southeastern Europe

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Abstract

The study exploits the air temperature and precipitation data from ERA5-Land reanalysis and E-OBS gridded observations that are freely available from the Copernicus Climate Change Service. The objectives of the study are to analyze the distribution of Köppen climate zones and to detect the changes in the presence and coverage of the specific climate types in Southeastern Europe. The results are shown separately for the following reference periods: 1961–1990, 1971–2000, 1981–2010, and 1991–2020. In the period 1961–1990, the most dominant climate type in Southeastern Europe was fully humid temperate climate with warm summer (Cfb), while fully humid continental climate with warm summer (Dfb) was also highly present there, together with fully humid temperate climate with hot summer (Cfa). In the period 1991–2020, the shift of Köppen climate zones appeared in such a way that the area with Dfb continental climate, that is often called snow or cold climate, is significantly reduced and this type is replaced with Cfb temperate climate. At the same time, Cfa climate type with hot summer is spread across wider area, mainly instead of Cfb with warm summer, now reaching almost the same percentage of coverage as Cfb type.

KEYWORDS

02. Climate variability, change & impacts, observational data analysis; 10. Tools and methods, climate; 11. Scale, mid-latitude; 14. Geographic/climatic zone, climate; 15. Application/context

1 | INTRODUCTION

Based on the Copernicus Climate Change Service report on ERA5 daily global surface air temperature anomaly, the boreal autumn September–November 2023 was the warmest on record globally with an average temperature of 15.3°C, which is 0.88°C above average (C3S, 2023). March 2024 is the 10th month in a row to be the hottest for the respective month in the ERA5 data record, going

back to 1940 (C3S, 2024), while the 12-month period April 2023 to March 2024 was 1.58°C above the pre-industrial level. The broader Mediterranean region is currently warming at faster rates than the global average and other regions with similar geographical and environmental characteristics (Urdiales-Flores et al., 2023). According to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, there is an increase in agricultural droughts in the Mediterranean

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region based on the changes observed in the total column of soil moisture (IPCC, 2021). This is a result of seasonal variations in the precipitation regime (Cook et al., 2016) associated with increasing heatwave frequency, intensity, and duration (Basarin et al., 2020). Prolonged droughts are causing environmental damage and have negative socio-economic impacts. A rain deficit and record-high temperatures in January 2024 impacted winter crops and fruit trees along the coasts of Spain, Italy, Greece, and the Mediterranean islands. In Morocco and Algeria, these conditions led to reduced crop growth (Tarnavsky et al., 2024).

Various climate indicators can be used to explore the changes in the air temperature and precipitation regimes over a specific area (Brown et al., 2010). For Southeastern Europe, which is a part of the Mediterranean region in a wider scope, several studies have examined the trends of different climate indices. Leščešen et al. (2023) used ERA5-Land precipitation data from 1961 to 2020 and analyzed the maximum one-day precipitation amount, showing predominantly positive trends in heavy precipitation events in various parts of Southeastern Europe, particularly during autumn. Malcheva et al. (2022) used daily temperature data from 70 meteorological stations located in the region of Southeastern Europe, collected during the period 1961–2020, and ERA5-Land data in gaps-filling procedures, to calculate several threshold indicators of extreme heat events, showing their increasing trends. Doshi et al. (2023) used E-OBS data during the period of 1950–2021 over the European regions and considered monthly values of 74 climate indices, which were divided into eight categories: temperature (32), precipitation (16), drought (15), multi-element (5), wind speed (3), global radiation (1), relative humidity (1), and sea level pressure (1). Trend analysis showed the highest increase in the number of warm days during August experienced by Bosnia and Herzegovina, being a part of Southeastern Europe. Tošić et al. (2023) used daily minimum and maximum temperatures from E-OBS gridded data set covering similar period for Serbia and showed significant changes in temperature extremes consistent with warming, especially during the summer season, with an increasing trend for mean maximum temperatures, hottest days, warm days, summer days, mean minimum temperatures, coldest nights, warm nights, and tropical nights.

Climatological studies that use station observations from specific countries consider a limited amount of data; nevertheless, they are providing relevant information. Based on observational data, Micu et al. (2021) showed a significant warming trend, well reflected by the strong decline in the number of frost days and icing days, and a significant increase in the absolute maximum

temperatures, the number of summer days and the warm spell duration in the Southern Carpathians, Romania, during the period 1961–2018. Calculation of the De Martonne aridity index in the non-mountainous part of Southern Bulgaria using the data from eight meteorological stations showed decreasing of aridity during the period 1986–2015 (Nikolova & Yanakiev, 2020). Čadro et al. (2023 and references herein) showed a positive trend of mean air temperature for Bosnia and Herzegovina and Croatia between two climate periods (1961–1990 and 1991–2020), while a trend of precipitation amount varied depending on the location. Tošić et al. (2016) used station data for Slovenia from 1961 to 2011 and found a significant decreasing trend in annual precipitation and an increasing trend in mean temperatures. Trend of percentile climate indices in Montenegro in the period 1961–2020 showed a significant warming and slight aridization (Burić & Doderović, 2022). Amiri and Gocić (2023) used monthly precipitation from 28 stations in Serbia during the period 1946–2019 to calculate several drought indicators and concluded that the regions with the highest amounts of the negative anomaly are the regions with the least amounts of precipitation. Mimić et al. (2017) even calculated Kolmogorov complexity by using the Lempel–Ziv algorithm on time series of the daily maximum and minimum air temperature and precipitation from the station observations in Serbia for the period 1951–2010. The results showed increasing randomness for the maximum temperature, decreasing randomness for the precipitation and no change for the minimum temperature.

To the best of our knowledge, none of the studies published in the last few years showed the changes in the Köppen climate zones in Southeastern Europe, although there are some local studies (Ács et al., 2020; Malcheva & Bocheva, 2023; Popov, 2018; Popov, 2022; Ruman, 2020). In this classification, the two most important meteorological elements are the air temperature and the precipitation, and all criteria are based on their values. Globally, it distinguishes five zones: tropical (A), arid (B), temperate (C), continental (D), and polar (E), considering vegetation groups. Specific climate types defined within this classification will be explained in Section 2 of the paper, which describes the materials and methods used in the study. However, Peel et al. (2007) updated the Köppen–Geiger classification with some modifications, which will also be explained in detail in Section 2. Beck et al. (2018) followed the proposed changes in their research covering the period 1980–2016 and considering the whole world. Mihailović et al. (2015) showed that, for example, in Serbia, predominant climate type for the period 1961–1990 is Cf, which is in line with previous research for that region, rather than Df type, according to updated classification.

The aim of this study was to investigate the change of Köppen climate zones between the two reference periods 1961–1990 and 1991–2020 in Southeastern Europe. The paper is organized in the following way. In Section 2, the description of the study area is presented as well as the data sets used, along with Köppen–Geiger climate classification. Next, the results are presented and discussed in Section 3 of the manuscript, which is concluded in Section 4.

2 | MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 | The study area

Southeastern Europe is a geographical subregion of Europe, consisting primarily of the Balkans, adjacent regions, and archipelagos. However, the concept of Southeastern Europe may vary in different geographical, political, or economic contexts (Mishkova, 2010). In this study, we considered a region bounded by the Ionian Sea, the Adriatic Sea, the Alps, the Pannonian Plain, and the Black Sea. This region consists of several mountain

ranges, such as the Dinarides, the Carpathian Mountains, the Balkan Mountains, and the highest mountain Rila, Pirin, and Rhodopes. Thus, the countries of Southeastern Europe, considered here, are the following: Slovenia, Croatia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Serbia, Montenegro, Albania, North Macedonia, Bulgaria, and Romania (Figure 1).

2.2 | Data sets

ERA5-Land is a reanalysis data set providing an accurate description of the climate of the past, created by the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts. It has been produced by replaying the land component of the ERA5 climate reanalysis, at an enhanced horizontal resolution of $0.1^\circ \times 0.1^\circ$ (i.e., native spatial resolution is 9 km) and hourly temporal resolution (Muñoz Sabater, 2019). Reanalysis combines model data with observations from across the world into a globally complete and consistent data set using the laws of physics, and it produces data that goes several decades back in time. The ERA5-Land data set, as with any other

FIGURE 1 The study area of Southeastern Europe. Source: Google Maps.

simulation, provides estimates that have some degree of uncertainty that grows as we go back in time, because the number of available observations is lower.

E-OBS is a daily gridded land-only observational data set over Europe, with horizontal resolution of $0.1^\circ \times 0.1^\circ$. The blended time series from the station network of the European Climate Assessment & Dataset (ECA&D) project forms the basis for the E-OBS gridded data set (Cornes et al., 2018). All station data are sourced directly from the European National Meteorological and Hydrological Services or other data-holding institutions. The observations cover 24 h per time step, but the exact period can be different per region and the reason for this is that some data providers measure from midnight to midnight while others might measure from morning to morning. However, it is made sure that the largest part of the measured 24-h period corresponds to the day attached to the time step in E-OBS. While it remains an important data set for the validation of climate models, E-OBS is also used more generally for monitoring the climate across Europe.

In this study, we used both ERA5-Land and E-OBS climate data sets, from 1961 to 2020, for Southeastern Europe. A sliding window including data for 30-year period was used to calculate climate types, with the shift of 10 years, in order to analyze sequential changes. This way, four different periods have been defined: 1961–1990, 1971–2000, 1981–2010, and 1991–2020, and the percentage of area covered with the specific climate type in a given region was considered. Additionally, a change in climate zones between the two nonoverlapping reference periods, 1961–1990 and 1991–2020, has been investigated in more detail. Data processing and calculations have been performed in Python.

2.3 | Köppen–Geiger climate classification

The description of Köppen–Geiger classification is presented in Table 1, by following the definition of the climate types given in Kottek et al. (2006). Each climate type is described with a group of three symbols. The third symbol is explained at the bottom of Table 1. Variables used in this classification are: the annual mean 2 m temperature (T_{ann}), the monthly mean temperature of the warmest (T_{max}) and coldest (T_{min}) month, the accumulated annual precipitation (P_{ann}), and the precipitation of the driest month (P_{min}). Additionally, Ps_{min} , Ps_{max} , Pw_{min} , and Pw_{max} refer to the lowest and highest

TABLE 1 The definition of criteria describing the climate types by Köppen–Geiger classification.

Type	Description	Criterion
A	Tropical climates	$T_{\text{min}} \geq 18^\circ\text{C}$
Af	Tropical rainforest, fully humid	$P_{\text{min}} \geq 60 \text{ mm}$
Am	Tropical monsoon	$P_{\text{ann}} \geq 25 (100 - P_{\text{min}})$
As	Tropical savannah with dry summer	$P_{\text{min}} < 60 \text{ mm}$ in summer
Aw	Tropical savannah with dry winter	$P_{\text{min}} < 60 \text{ mm}$ in winter
B	Arid climates	$P_{\text{ann}} < 10 P_{\text{th}}$
BS	Steppe climate	$P_{\text{ann}} > 5 P_{\text{th}}$
BW	Desert climate	$P_{\text{ann}} \leq 5 P_{\text{th}}$
C	Temperate climates	$-3^\circ\text{C} < T_{\text{min}} < 18^\circ\text{C}$
Cs	Temperate climate with dry summer	$Ps_{\text{min}} < Pw_{\text{min}}$, $Pw_{\text{max}} > 3$ Ps_{min} , and $Ps_{\text{min}} < 40 \text{ mm}$
Cw	Temperate climate with dry winter	$Pw_{\text{min}} < Ps_{\text{min}}$ and $Ps_{\text{max}} > 10$ Pw_{min}
Cf	Temperate climate, fully humid	Neither Cs nor Cw
D	Continental climates	$T_{\text{min}} \leq -3^\circ\text{C}$
Ds	Continental climate with dry summer	$Ps_{\text{min}} < Pw_{\text{min}}$, $Pw_{\text{max}} > 3$ Ps_{min} , and $Ps_{\text{min}} < 40 \text{ mm}$
Dw	Continental climate with dry winter	$Pw_{\text{min}} < Ps_{\text{min}}$ and $Ps_{\text{max}} > 10$ Pw_{min}
Df	Continental climate, fully humid	Neither Ds nor Dw
E	Polar climates	$T_{\text{max}} < 10^\circ\text{C}$
ET	Tundra climate	$0^\circ\text{C} \leq T_{\text{max}} < 10^\circ\text{C}$
EF	Frost climate	$T_{\text{max}} < 0^\circ\text{C}$
h	Hot steppe/desert	$T_{\text{ann}} \geq 18^\circ\text{C}$
k	Cold steppe/desert	$T_{\text{ann}} < 18^\circ\text{C}$
a	Hot summer	$T_{\text{max}} \geq 22^\circ\text{C}$
b	Warm summer	Not (a) and at least 4 $T_{\text{mon}} \geq 10^\circ\text{C}$
c	Cool summer and cold winter	Not (b) and $T_{\text{min}} > -38^\circ\text{C}$
d	Extremely continental	Like (c) but $T_{\text{min}} \leq -38^\circ\text{C}$

monthly precipitation for the summer and winter half-year, respectively. All temperature values are given in $^\circ\text{C}$, while monthly and annual precipitation are in mm. Additionally, precipitation thresholds P_{th} , used for the calculation of B climate types, are defined within Equation (1).

$$P_{\text{th}} = \begin{cases} 2\{T_{\text{ann}}\} & \text{if at least } \frac{2}{3} \text{ of the annual precipitation occurs in winter,} \\ 2\{T_{\text{ann}}\} + 28 & \text{if at least } \frac{2}{3} \text{ of the annual precipitation occurs in summer,} \\ 2\{T_{\text{ann}}\} + 14 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Peel et al. (2007) used a higher value of 0°C instead of -3°C as a threshold for the temperature of the coldest month in D climate type. In updated classification, for Cs and Ds types, the authors excluded the criterion that the lowest monthly precipitation for the summer half-year ($P_{\text{s}_{\text{min}}}$) is less than the lowest monthly precipitation for the winter half-year ($P_{\text{w}_{\text{min}}}$), and for Cw and Dw types, they excluded the opposite criterion, respectively. In C climate type, the third symbol c can have 1–4 months with the average temperature greater or equal to 10°C , while in the original classification, it is greater than or equal to 4 months. Also, for D climate type, in the case of the third symbol c, they excluded the criterion that the temperature of the coldest month is greater than -38°C . Additionally, Aw type, typical for Savannah, does not follow the criterion that the precipitation of the driest month (P_{min}) is less than 60 mm in winter, while there is no defined As type. To mention here that continental climates denoted with D are also called snow climates (Kottek et al., 2006) or cold climates (Peel et al., 2007).

3 | RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Here, we present the distribution of Köppen climate zones in Southeastern Europe during the indicated reference periods and detect the changes in the presence and coverage of the specific climate types, defined by the temperature and precipitation regimes. The results are shown separately for the following periods: 1961–1990 (Figure 2), 1971–2000 (Figure 3), 1981–2010 (Figure 4), and 1991–2020 (Figure 5). Animation of the temporal changes of spatial distribution of represented climate types in the region of interest is given in Video S1 (ERA5-Land) and Video S2 (E-OBS).

In the period 1961–1990 (Figure 2) the most dominant climate type in Southeastern Europe is Cfb (fully humid temperate climate with warm summer), while Dfb (fully humid continental climate with warm summer) is present in northwestern Slovenia (the Alps), central parts of Bosnia and Herzegovina, northern Montenegro and southwestern Serbia (the Dinarides), western North Macedonia (the Sharr mountain), eastern Serbia and

FIGURE 2 Climate types for the period 1961–1990 obtained with ERA5-Land (a) and E-OBS (b).

FIGURE 3 Climate types for the period 1971–2000 obtained with ERA5-Land (a) and E-OBS (b).

FIGURE 4 Climate types for the period 1981–2010 obtained with ERA5-Land (a) and E-OBS (b).

western Bulgaria (the Balkan mountains), southern Bulgaria (the Rhodopes) and major parts of Romania (the Carpathian mountains). Cfa type (fully humid temperate climate with hot summer) is localized in southern Romania, northern and southern Bulgaria, central parts of North Macedonia, and according to ERA5-Land data in northern Serbia (Figure 2a), which cannot be seen in E-OBS data (Figure 2b). Csa and Csb types can be found mainly in Albania and at the Croatian coast.

In the period 1971–2000 (Figure 3), there was a decrease in area with Dfb type mostly in Romania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, and Serbia, while there was a spread of Cfa type in northern Serbia, again according to

ERA5-Land data (Figure 3a), but not according to E-OBS data (Figure 3b).

In the period 1981–2010 (Figure 4), both data sets show the increasing area for Cs types (temperate climate with dry summer), that is, Csa (with hot summer) and Csb (with warm summer), in the coastal area of Croatia, Montenegro, and Albania. Cfa type is further spreading in northern Serbia, northern Croatia, eastern Romania, and northern Bulgaria.

In the period 1991–2020 (Figure 5), the area with Cfa type is almost equal to the area covered with Cfb type in Southeastern Europe. Dfb type is still evident mostly in Romania and partially in Montenegro, but almost

FIGURE 5 Climate types for the period 1991–2020 obtained with ERA5-Land (a) and E-OBS (b).

TABLE 2 The percentage of area covered with the specific climate type in Southeastern Europe for the defined periods.

Data set	Period	Climate type								
		BSk	Csa	Csb	Cfa	Cfb	Cfc	Dfb	Dfc	ET
ERA5-Land	1961–1990	0	1.19	1.23	13.77	52.24	0	31	0.57	0
	1971–2000	0	1.41	1.35	18.7	60.33	0	17.37	0.85	0
	1981–2010	0	3.01	1.28	29.69	51.09	0	14.26	0.67	0
	1991–2020	0	2.54	0.73	39.59	44.94	0	11.76	0.44	0
E-OBS	1961–1990	0.66	4.2	3.11	12.04	50.66	0	26.3	2.97	0.07
	1971–2000	1	3.91	2.95	14.81	58.93	0.03	14.94	3.4	0.03
	1981–2010	0.73	4.77	3.04	25.71	50.34	0.03	12.61	2.77	0
	1991–2020	0.46	4.44	1.83	38.04	41.92	0.06	11.17	2.08	0

vanished in the other countries. Again, Csa and Csb types are mainly present in Albania.

The percentage of area covered with the specific climate type in the considered region is given in Table 2 for each defined period. First thing to be noted is that some specific climate types, such as BSk (cold steppe climate), Cfc (fully humid temperate climate with cool summer and cold winter), and ET (tundra climate) existed in less than or equal to 1% of the area according to E-OBS data but were not existing according to ERA5-Land data. Thus, they will be neglected in the analysis.

The most prominent changes are noticed for Cfa and Dfb types, and are being aligned between ERA5-Land and E-OBS data. The area with Cfa type increased from 13.77% (1961–1990) to 39.59% (1991–2020) according to ERA5-Land, while it increased from 12.04% (1961–1990) to 38.04% (1991–2020) according to E-OBS. The area with Dfb type decreased from 31% (1961–1990) to 11.76%

(1991–2020) according to ERA5-Land, while it decreased from 26.3% (1961–1990) to 11.17% (1991–2020) according to E-OBS. Both ERA5-Land and E-OBS identify Cfb as the most represented climate type in the region, having some oscillation in the coverage during four considered periods. However, the total area decreased from the 1961–1990 period to the 1991–2020 period by approximately 8% in both cases. Both Csa and Csb are facing changes in the coverage roughly by only 1%. It should be mentioned that these two climate types are a bit more present with E-OBS data than ERA5-Land data. The reason for this must be in different methodologies that were used to generate these two data sets. The changes in coverage of Dfc type (fully humid continental climate with cool summer and cold winter) are mostly negligible.

A positive trend of the mean air temperature for Bosnia and Herzegovina and Croatia between two climate periods, 1961–1990 and 1991–2020, that is shown

by Čadro et al. (2023), is reflected in the shift of climate zones from Dfb to Cfb in Bosnia and Herzegovina, and from Cfb to Cfa and Csa in Croatia. A decrease of the area with Dfb climate type in Montenegro is in line with the findings of Burić and Doderović (2022) about significant warming. Malcheva and Bocheva (2023) ascertained the shift of climate types in Bulgaria between the two reference periods, 1961–1990 and 1991–2020, showing that hotter and dryer subtypes of temperate climates expand their coverage, corresponding to the reduction of the cold climate subtypes, which can also be seen in our results (Video S1). Popov (2018) calculated climate types for several stations in the Vardar, Struma, and Mesta river valleys (parts of North Macedonia and Bulgaria) during the second half of 20th century and the beginning of 21st century, and showed the presence of Cfa, Cfb and Csa types in that region, indicating climate variations between different 30-year periods similar to our results. For Serbia, it is shown that there is a shift of climate zones from Cfb to Cfa and in some mountain parts from Dfb to Cfb, and that the changes are happening much faster than expected (Mihailović et al., 2015). These results are in line with the findings by Ruman (2020) which corroborate the fact that the warming trend is the main driver of transitions of climate types. According to some projections, further shift of climate zones can be expected by the end of the 21st century in Southeastern Europe and the Pannonian Basin (Ruman & Ruman, 2023).

4 | CONCLUSIONS

The regional and national studies showed the change of several climate indices during the period from 1961 to 2020 in Southeastern Europe. In this study, we presented the change of climate zones in the considered region by comparing two reference periods, 1961–1990 and 1991–2020. For that, we used the Köppen–Geiger climate classification and followed the criteria defining different climate types given by Kottke et al. (2006). This study also promotes the usage of open data sets from relevant sources, as much faster way of achieving results and insights into climate change. It exploits the air temperature and precipitation data from ERA5-Land reanalysis and E-OBS gridded observations that are freely available from the Copernicus Climate Change Service, through the Climate Data Store. The same material and method can be used to analyze the shift of climate zones for any region of interest in Europe, and in the case of ERA5-Land for the whole world. Although it is shown in the paper that there are slight variations in the presence and coverage of some

specific climate types when comparing ERA5-Land and E-OBS data, the detected changes are more or less consistent between the two data sets. The reason for this must be in different methodologies that were used to generate these two data sets. In the period 1961–1990, the most dominant type in Southeastern Europe was fully humid temperate climate with warm summer (Cfb), while fully humid continental climate with warm summer (Dfb) is also highly present there, together with fully humid temperate climate with hot summer (Cfa). In the period 1991–2020, the shift of Köppen climate zones appeared in such a way that the area with Dfb continental climate is significantly reduced and this type is replaced with Cfb temperate climate. At the same time, Cfa climate type with hot summer is spread across wider area, mainly instead of Cfb with warm summer, now reaching almost the same percentage of coverage as Cfb type. These changes are depicting the shift of climate zones toward warmer climates in Southeastern Europe.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Gordan Mimić: Conceptualization; methodology; investigation; writing – original draft. **Zorica Podračanin:** Data curation; formal analysis; visualization; software; writing – review and editing. **Biljana Basarin:** Writing – review and editing; funding acquisition; project administration.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in the Climate Data Store at <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/home>.

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REFERENCES

- Ács, F., Zsákai, A., Kristóf, E., Szabó, A.I. & Breuer, H. (2020) Carpathian Basin climate according to Köppen and a clothing resistance scheme. *Theoretical and Applied Climatology*, 141(1), 299–307.
- Amiri, M.A. & Gocić, M. (2023) Analysis of temporal and spatial variations of drought over Serbia by investigating the applicability of precipitation-based drought indices. *Theoretical and Applied Climatology*, 154(1–2), 261–274. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00704-023-04554-6>
- Basarin, B., Lukić, T. & Matzarakis, A. (2020) Review of biometeorology of heatwaves and warm extremes in Europe. *Atmosphere*, 11(12), 1276. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3390/atmos11121276>
- Beck, H., Zimmermann, N., McVicar, T., Vergopolan, N., Berg, A. & Wood, E.F. (2018) Present and future Köppen–Geiger climate classification maps at 1-km resolution. *Scientific*

- Data, 5, 180214. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2018.214>
- Brown, P.J., Bradley, R.S. & Keimig, F.T. (2010) Changes in extreme climate indices for the northeastern United States, 1870–2005. *Journal of Climate*, 23, 6555–6572. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1175/2010JCLI3363.1>
- Burić, D. & Doderović, M. (2022) Trend of percentile climate indices in Montenegro in the period 1961–2020. *Sustainability*, 14(19), 12519. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3390/su141912519>
- C3S. (2023) Copernicus Climate Change Service. Available from: <https://climate.copernicus.eu/2023-track-be-hottest-year-ever-whats-next> [Accessed 19th December 2023].
- C3S. (2024) Copernicus Climate Change Service. Available from: <https://climate.copernicus.eu/march-2024-10th-consecutive-record-warm-month-globally> [Accessed 22nd April 2024].
- Čadro, S., Uzunović, M., Marković, M., Žurovec, O. & Gocić, M. (2023) Climate change impacts on water balance components in Bosnia and Herzegovina and Croatia. *Agriculture and Forestry*, 69(2), 101–116. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.17707/AgricForest.69.2.08>
- Cook, B.I., Anchukaitis, K.J., Touchan, R., Meko, D.M. & Cook, E.R. (2016) Spatiotemporal drought variability in the Mediterranean over the last 900 years. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 121, 2060–2074. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1002/2015JD023929>
- Cornes, R., van der Schrier, G., van den Besselaar, E.J.M. & Jones, P. (2018) An ensemble version of the E-OBS temperature and precipitation datasets. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 123, 9391–9409. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1029/2017JD028200>
- Doshi, S.C., Lohmann, G., Rambu, N. & Ionita, M. (2023) Spatio-temporal trend analysis of climate indices for the European continent. *Journal of Water and Climate Change*, 14(9), 3112–3130. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.2166/wcc.2023.183>
- IPCC. (2021) Summary for policymakers. In: Masson-Delmotte, V., Zhai, P., Pirani, A., Connors, S.L., Péan, C., Berger, S. et al. (Eds.) *Climate change 2021: the physical science basis. Contribution of working group I to the sixth assessment report of the intergovernmental panel on climate change*, Vol. 2021. Cambridge; New York, NY: Cambridge University Press, pp. 3–32.
- Kottek, M., Grieser, J., Beck, C., Rudolf, B. & Rubel, F. (2006) World map of the Köppen-Geiger climate classification updated. *Meteorologische Zeitschrift*, 15, 259–263.
- Leščešen, I., Basarin, B., Podračanin, Z. & Mesaroš, M. (2023) Changes in annual and seasonal extreme precipitation over southeastern Europe. *Environmental Sciences Proceedings*, 26(1), 48. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3390/environsciproc2023026048>
- Malcheva, K. & Bocheva, L. (2023) Assessment of contemporary climate change in Bulgaria using the Köppen-Geiger climate classification. In: Dobrinkova, N. & Nikolov, O. (Eds.) *Environmental protection and disaster risks. EnviroRISKS 2022. Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems*, Vol. 638. Cham: Springer. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-26754-3_12
- Malcheva, K., Bocheva, L. & Chervenkov, H. (2022) Spatio-temporal variation of extreme heat events in southeastern Europe. *Atmosphere*, 13, 1186. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3390/atmos13081186>
- Micu, D.M., Amihaesei, V.A., Milian, N. & Cheval, S. (2021) Recent changes in temperature and precipitation indices in the Southern Carpathians, Romania (1961–2018). *Theoretical and Applied Climatology*, 144(1), 691–710.
- Mihailović, D.T., Lalić, B., Drešković, N., Mimić, G., Djurdjević, V. & Jančić, M. (2015) Climate change effects on crop yields in Serbia and related shifts of Köppen climate zones under the SRES-A1B and SRES-A2. *International Journal of Climatology*, 35, 3320–3334. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1002/joc.4209>
- Mimić, G., Mihailović, D.T. & Kapor, D. (2017) Complexity analysis of the air temperature and the precipitation time series in Serbia. *Theoretical and Applied Climatology*, 127, 891–898. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00704-015-1677-6>
- Mishkova, D. (2010) What is in Balkan history? Spaces and scales in the tradition of Southeast-European studies. *Southeastern Europe*, 34(1), 55–86. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1163/187633309X12563839996621>
- Muñoz Sabater, J. (2019) ERA5-Land hourly data from 1950 to present. Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) Climate Data Store (CDS). Available from: <https://doi.org/10.24381/cds.e2161bac> [Accessed 9th May 2024].
- Nikolova, N. & Yanakiev, D. (2020) Climate aridity in southern Bulgaria for the period 1961–2015. *Forum Geographic*, 19, 10–17. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.5775/fg.2020.010.i>
- Peel, M.C., Finlayson, B.L. & McMahon, T.A. (2007) Updated world map of the Köppen-Geiger climate classification. *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences*, 11, 1633–1644. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-11-1633-2007>
- Popov, H. (2018) Local climates of Vardar, Struma and Mesta valleys (Balkan Peninsula) according to the modified Köppen climate classification. *Bulletin of the Serbian Geographical Society*, 98(1), 79–90. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.2298/GSGD180428005P>
- Popov, H. (2022) Using Köppen climate classification like diagnostic tool to quantify climate variation in Lower Danube Valley for the period 1961–2017. In: Negm, A., Zaharia, L. & Ioana-Toroimac, G. (Eds.) *The Lower Danube River: hydro-environmental issues and sustainability*. Cham, Switzerland: Springer International Publishing, pp. 255–271.
- Ruman, A. (2020) Modelling climate types in South Pannonian Basin, Serbia by applying the Köppen-Geiger climate classification. *Modeling Earth System and Environment*, 6, 1303–1313. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40808-020-00773-2>
- Ruman, A. & Ruman, A. (2023) Köppen-Geiger climate classification in the Pannonian Basin according to SSP5-8.5 scenario. *International Journal of Atmospheric and Oceanic Sciences*, 7(2), 31–49. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.ijaos.20230702.12>
- Tarnavsky, E., Rossi, M., Bussay, A., Morel, J., Biavetti, I., Bratu, M. et al. (2024) JRC MARS Bulletin - Crop monitoring in Europe—January 2024 Vol. 32 No 1, Vandenberg, M. (Ed.). Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/10.2760/03283>
- Tošić, I., Tošić, M., Lazić, I., Aleksandrov, N., Putniković, S. & Djurdjević, V. (2023) Spatio-temporal changes in the mean and

extreme temperature indices for Serbia. *International Journal of Climatology*, 43(5), 2391–2410. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1002/joc.7981>

Tošić, I., Zorn, M., Ortar, J., Unkašević, M., Gavrilov, M.B. & Marković, S.B. (2016) Annual and seasonal variability of precipitation and temperatures in Slovenia from 1961 to 2011. *Atmospheric Research*, 168, 220–233. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosres.2015.09.014>

Urdiales-Flores, D., Zittis, G., Hadjinicolaou, P., Osipov, S., Klingmüller, K., Mihalopoulos, N. et al. (2023) Drivers of accelerated warming in Mediterranean climate-type regions. *npj Climate and Atmospheric Science*, 6, 97. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41612-023-00423-1>

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section at the end of this article.

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